

Molecular Docking of Accessible Cannabinoid GPR55 Antagonists: Achieving Binding Energies Exceeding -10.6 kcal/mol and Predicted Similar Potency Over PSB-SB-487 Human G-PROTEIN RECEPTOR 55

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Abstract

CID16020046 is the most readily available and widely used GPR55 inverse agonist, despite its relatively complex heterochemical structure. Psb-SB-487 is less readily available, although it exhibits higher affinity for the receptor and greater selectivity. Clearly, availability is often a priority in both experimental pharmacology and industrial pharmaceuticals. This work demonstrates the molecular docking of GPR55 receptor antagonists with extremely accessible synthesis and ease of use, as well as higher affinity than CID16020046 and comparable to Psb-SB-487. The presented structures are water-soluble amino acid derivatives of BENZOIN, characterized by high lipophilicity and water solubility, simple and accessible pharmacological synthesis, and the absence of highly toxic ligands:

CurPocket ID	Vina 17 score	Cavity 17 volume (Å ³)	Center (x, y, z)	Docking size (x, y, z)
⊙C1	-10.6	2747	15, 5, -7	26, 26, 35
⊙C4	-8.8	168	6, -2, 13	26, 26, 26
⊙C2	-8.4	549	-15, -9, 15	26, 26, 26
⊙C3	-7.6	346	-25, 2, 13	26, 26, 26

Cc5cccc(CN(CCOC2ccc1cc(C(=O)O)ccc1c2)C(C(=O)c3cccc(C)c3)c4cccc(C)c4)c5

Keywords: Cannabinoid GPR55 receptor (Q9Y2T6) antagonists, GPR55 antagonists, Molecular Docking, AutoDock Vina, High-affinity ligand

Figure 2

One of the simplest and most readily available derivatives, it contains no toxic ligands, is easy to use, and exhibits relatively high affinity for the receptor. Like the previous structure, this tautomer does not contain exposed hydrophilic radicals in the plug region and does not form hydrogen bonds with the receptor, eliminating the possibility of agonistic effects.

Selected molecular docking structures demonstrate high accessibility, convenience, and fine-tuning of affinity. Structures attached to this work as supplementary material contain alternative cores that are also characterized by ease of synthesis and specific strategies for implementing the antagonist effect: deep and superficial binding, the absence and presence of hydrophilic radicals in the structure, the potential for binding to the CB2 receptor, as well as the likely complete lack of potential for agonism with the CB2 receptor, and varying degrees of lipophilicity and bioavailability.

The supplementary materials include visualizations of dozens of structures featuring with affinities ranging from -8 to -10.6 kcal/mol. These materials provide docking data, interactive HTML reports, and videos demonstrating volumetric renderings of the complexes.

Methods

Since no high-resolution crystal structure covers the full conformational flexibility required for this study, the AlphaFold Monomer v2.0 prediction for the Human Cannabinoid Receptor G-PROTEIN COUPLED RECEPTOR 55 (Q9Y2T6) was utilized as the receptor model.

Blind docking was performed via the CB-Dock2 server, utilizing the CurPocket algorithm for automated cavity detection. The docking simulations were conducted using AutoDock Vina, with additional geometric validation provided by FitDock.